

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Willful Ignorance and Moral Behavior"

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Willful Ignorance and Moral Behavior". To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Joshua Tasoff](#)
2. [Romain Espinosa](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment: We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice."

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5):¹ On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in? (See ranking tiers discussed [here](#).) *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Anonymous evaluator 1	90	4.0
Anonymous evaluator 2	88	4.7

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).²

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.³

Evaluation summaries

Joshua Tasoff

The paper is professionally written and the experiment is well-designed. The main result, avoiders of a VR animal advocacy message exhibit larger treatment effects on consumption than information seekers, is novel and important. I find the claims about the dynamics of the treatment effect to be less supported by the evidence. It is more speculative.

Romain Espinosa

This study is an outstanding work that will become a major reference in the empirical literature about information avoidance and meat consumption. First, the authors make here a highly valuable contribution to the economic discipline and, in particular, to the research on dietary transitions by determining the causal impact of information provision on individuals conditional on their a priori willingness to get informed. This is an important research point both for economics in general (where the question of information avoidance has been discussed intensively over the past five years) and for dietary transitions, where researchers and society struggle to induce dietary changes (changes which are needed in light of the environmental, health, and ethical issues arising from large scale meat consumption in developed countries). Second, the authors came up with a lab & field design with real consumption choices, which has been relatively rare in the empirical literature on dietary changes. Following individuals outside of the lab is a key element [for considering] issues like displacement or long-term effects. In addition, looking at effective dietary choices is central, as the attitude-behavior gap in nutrition is a major limiting factor for this research literature. Here, the authors also show that the effect of watching the video on effective consumption choices is short-lived. Third, on the estimation side, the authors propose a neat empirical strategy to elicit the conditional impact (addressing the issue of self-selection), discuss the potential problems at length (e.g., displacement of meat consumption), clearly expose the deviations from their pre-analysis plan, and carefully thought about numerous design issues (e.g., the alternative video). Overall, I am very supportive of this work.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.^[1]

	Evaluator 1 Joshua Tasoff			Evaluator 2 Romain Espinosa		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁴	90	(75, 96)		88	(83, 93)	
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁵	75	(33, 92)	⁶	85	(80, 90)	⁷

Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁸	60	(20, 80)	9	85	(80, 90)	10
Logic & communication 11	75	(33, 92)		85	(80, 90)	12
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹³	75	(33, 92)		50	(50, 50)	14
Real-world relevance ¹⁵	75	(33, 92)		90	(85, 95)	16
Relevance to global priorities ¹⁷	75	(33, 92)		100	(100, 100)	18

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 Joshua Tasoff			Evaluator 2 Romain Espinosa		
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.0	(3.5, 4.3)		4.7	(4.4, 5.0)	

What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	3.4	(2.8, 4.0)	19	4.3	(4.0, 4.6)	20
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 					

Unjournal process notes

Why we prioritized this work

Animal welfare advocates argue that consumption of animal products through factory farming leads to massive suffering, and reducing this consumption could substantially reduce this. A range of interventions aimed at influencing individual behavior have been considered, but there is very limited evidence on whether these are successful. Indeed, effective altruism linked animal welfare advocates have moved away from this approach in favor of corporate campaigns.

However, this may be from a lack of evidence rather than evidence that these interventions are ineffective. Of course, there may be heterogeneity; these interventions may be more effective for some audiences than others. It may matter whether these initiatives and ads are targeted towards 'seekers', neutral people, or even potential 'avoiders'. E.g., we could compare 'push' vs 'pull' marketing, ads targeted towards those showing interest in animals versus more neutral or 'surprise' ads etc.

The authors' work seems to have several rare and valuable strengths:

- a credible strategy for differentiating the effects of such information/stimuli on avoiders versus seekers, in a way that seems robust to differential selection issues.
- incentivized choices (of food vouchers)
- more consequential *field* evidence (linked to the lab experiment treatments?), with perhaps less potential for demand effects, temporary agreeability bias, etc.

In a general sense, The Unjournal is seeking to stimulate more rigorous social science research relevant to animal welfare, including a focus on consumption attitudes. This is one of our first forays in this direction.

What we asked evaluators to consider

We shared the manager's notes linked [here](#). Excerpting:

Consistent with The Unjournal's stated mission, and approach... We are interested in the specific applied and empirical questions, and in the implications of this for animal welfare marketing interventions, and interventions in adjacent areas.

These notes presented a range of fairly specific suggestions for evaluators to consider, as well as Nicolas Treich's previous notes for the authors.

Evaluation process

The authors were aware of this process and happy to have us give feedback on their work, sharing the most recent version of the paper.

Conflict of interest considerations

One of the evaluators is a member of The Unjournal's broad team. However, they did not play a decisive role in prioritizing this paper for evaluation.

References

[1] Epperson, Raphael and Gerster, Andreas, Willful Ignorance and Moral Behavior (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3938994> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3938994>

Footnotes

1. See "1 Mar 2024 note" above. ↵
2. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. ↵
3. See "1 Mar 2024 note" above. See [here](#) to learn how this changed, and to see the earlier instructions. ↵
- 4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

↵

- 5.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

↵

6. I think this is more of a basic science paper combined with treatment effects on what particular intervention. ↵

7. This work is very informative about the challenges that empirical research on dietary changes faces. It combines several strengths that are seldom jointly present in other empirical works: revealed preferences, lab and field data, and randomization at the individual level. The results will help NGOs and policymakers in supporting/stimulating dietary transitions and will benefit the scientific community (positive relationship between information avoidance and information elasticity). ↵

8. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? ↵

9. The methods seem reasonable. I'm not an expert on econometrics and the IPW estimator so I was unable to assess this. ↵

10.

The experimental design is very well done and clearly exposed. The empirical methods are sound and the authors present convincing evidence about the most immediate robustness concerns.

↵

11. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? ↵

12. The paper is written clearly and all arguments are well presented. ↵

13.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

↵

14. I have not seen any link to the data and codes. I assume that the data are too sensitive to be shared (individual-level consumption data with identifiers). So, this category would not be applicable. (So, I indicated 50.) [↵](#)

15.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↵](#)

16. Very relevant as such videos are widely spread and viewed in society. The only departure from reality might be the 360° dimension. [↵](#)

17. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

18. The topic of the paper (industrial animal farming) is one of the greatest challenges our societies currently face. Congratulations to the authors for addressing such an important topic. [↵](#)

19. Unfortunately, it is not yet clear whether animal-welfare economics has enough buy-in from the profession to be considered a subject of interest. I think there is a greater than average risk that the paper would be under-placed. [↵](#)

20. I fear that some editors in top economic journals are still reluctant to publish works related to animal welfare. So, I think there is a risk of this paper being underpublished. [↵](#)

References

1. [↵](#)

2. Epperson, Raphael and Gerster, Andreas, Willful Ignorance and Moral Behavior (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3938994> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3938994> [↵](#)